

PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM OF PREPARING FUTURE EDUCATORS FOR THE FORMATION OF LIFE SKILLS

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Annotation.

this article is written in education about connecting theory with practice, generating awareness and activity in students, allowing self-assessment, the formation of skills about life, the delivery of the true essence of the lessons of fiction to the reader, etc.

Keywords.

education, theory, practice, students, consciousness, assessment, fiction.

In ancient Greece, a teacher (ancient Greek *pydiagus*, "the one who leads the child") is a slave whose care in Athenian families is entrusted to boys from the age of seven. The duties of the teacher included protecting the student from physical and spiritual dangers and primary literacy until the child entered school. The teacher had to accompany his student to school or class and be inseparable from him when leaving home, under the strictest responsibility.

Slaves were generally chosen as teachers who were not suitable for any other work, but distinguished by their loyalty to the House. Usually they were foreigners-often Thracians or Asians who speak poorly in Greek. At the end of the Roman Republic, the practice of holding a teacher in the family passed to the Romans, especially to teach the Greek language. The teacher performed his duties until the student matured. There were also female teachers, Greek teachers with young children. During the Empire, teachers were also referred to as slaves who taught all the tasks and methods of serving slaves to young slaves who were bought or raised at home. Such Apprentice slaves (*capillati*) lived together in a room called the *pedagogium*, led by tutors – teachers, assistant pedagogues and deans; they were also called *Pueri pedagogiani* or *payagogia*

After the Republic of Uzbekistan gained political independence, fundamental reforms began to be carried out in all spheres of our social life. On the basis of the totalitarian method of government, the task of solving the problem that has arisen

in recent decades, both in the system of popular education in business, has prompted significant changes in the Government of the Republic and in the educational system of the organized society.

Education of students to life in the educational process is one of the pressing issues of today's day. For this, of course, it is necessary that each educator correctly organizes the educational process, connecting it with practical life. The principle of associating theory with practice in education makes this process even easier. The creation of awareness and activity in students, allowing them to self-evaluate, and the delivery of the true essence of the lessons of fiction to the reader will help to form life skills in the educator.

Who pleases the memory of a mentally ill person

He is prosperous when Kagba is destroyed.

(A.Navoi)

If we analyze this verse of Alisher Navoi, then we can clearly see the egotistical, loving attitude of a person to others: YAGNI, if anyone who has lost heart and saves him from the heart of a sad person, helps to ease his grief, fills his grief with joy again, let him know that he will be able to apply to the work that is equal to the It turns out that this byte promotes the fact that each individual should not be indifferent to the lifestyle of those around him, to find solutions to the social, economic problems that have arisen in his life, to fight to end mental-psychological tension. By doing this, a person will have given the light of life again to a fading heart in society.

Individualization of a person is the development of his "self", thus forming a humane educational system in a broad sense. The purpose of such an approach in upbringing is to provide assistance to children, in the organization of their "subjective existence". To do this, in this educational system, special tools are developed that help a person to realize himself and realize himself. The subject of the humanitarian educational system is no longer only an educator, but also the children themselves. In this, both teachers and students jointly clarify their goals facing the higher educational institution, raise them to the level of practical tasks and carry them out together. An important condition for the effectiveness of the humanitarian educational system is the unification of students and adults into a common community. The relationship between children and adults, which creates certain relationships, first of all determines the educational capabilities of the system.

In conclusion, we can say that the education of students in the educational process to life is one of the pressing issues of today's day. For this, of course, it is necessary that each educator correctly organizes the educational process, connecting it with practical life. The principle of associating theory with practice in education makes this process even easier. The creation of awareness and activity in students, allowing them to self-evaluate, and the delivery of the true essence of the lessons of fiction to the reader will help to form life skills in the educator.

REFERENCES:

1. Richard E. Boyatzis. David C. McClelland: For The Wiley Encyclopedia of Personality and Individual Differences Volume IV: Clinical, Applied and Cross – Cultural Research. December 5, 2016
2. J.Raven (1984). Competence in modern society: Its Identification, Development and Release. – UK. P.220
3. Маркова А.К. Психология профессионализма. – М.: Знание, 1996. – 340 с.
4. Tuychieva Inoyatkhon. "Mechanisms Ensuring Children's Thought Activity Development at Preschool Education Process." Eastern European Scientific Journal 6 (2018).
5. Makhmutovna Tojiboyeva Khilolaxon, Tuychiyeva Inoyatkhon Ibragimovna. "Specific features of the pedagogical process focused on increasing the social activity of youth." Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR) 9.6 (2020): 165-171.
6. Tuychieva Inoyatkhon "THE PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM OF PREPARING BOYS FOR FAMILY RELATIONSHIPS IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS." 湖南大学学报 (自然科学版) 48.8 (2021).
7. A.Madvaliyev tahriri ostida, 2-jild. - Toshkent: O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi, 2006. – 408 b.